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THE FUTURE ENGINEER

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What will Engineering Education look like in 2030? Do you want to take part in the visionary work on future engineering education?

A growing gap between education and societal needs is reported, and it is imperative to close this gap to respond to today's and future challenges. The challenges that need to be met to enable tomorrow's engineers to meet society's needs are many, but the three challenges mentioned below that have been chosen to frame this study on the future development of engineering education.

- A. The need to integrate sustainable development as a red thread through all education has existed for a long time, and with the formation of the 17 sustainability development goals (SDGs) in combination with the contemporary climate debate, this need is even more obvious regarding engineering education in 2030 than it is now.
- B. Another challenge is posed by the industry demand for engineers who are experienced in project management and who have the ability to learn and adapt quickly, given that career paths will change more rapidly in the near future. Therefore, these future requirements for employability, including innovativeness and entrepreneurialism, constitute an important second challenge.
- C. A third major challenge is digitalisation, which comprises the increased system understanding and process skills that are integral parts of the fourth industrial revolution with an expected increase in the use of new technologies, like the Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence (AI), robotics, etc. Digitalisation will saturate the entire society and affect all the engineering disciplines.

The workshop is based on a "Nordic Engineering Hub" established in 2018 with the objective to empower the Nordic region when it comes to STEM education and in particular to address these three challenges. One project within the hub is on engineering education 2030 for which experts in various engineering subjects are interviewed.

What is seen during a first step of analysis is that the expectations seem to be quite contradictory, and variations are found to be dependent on what engineering discipline

you belong to. The more science-based engineers, such as chemical-engineers or physics-engineers seem to have a different picture on what will be important for the future than engineering disciplines that are more closely related to production, like mechanical or civil engineering. It is therefore very interesting for us and the participants in this workshop to see whether we find a consensus on how engineering education needs to be developed in order to meet future challenges.

Similar questions will form the basis for guided discussion in teams formed by the workshop leaders. With the reference to the three challenges, we ask the following main questions to the participants:

- How do think these challenges affect the development of your discipline and the educational program you are involved in?
- How would this look in 10 years time from now?
- Are your students are prepared for the future with the existing education?
- How will the students learn engineering in the future?
- Are there other challenges that we have not mentioned?

The workshop participants will be asked to establish teams around their subjects. Each team will be given a set of cards with possible directions of engineering education 2030 for each of the challenges. The participants will then have to choose three cards for each of the challenges and discuss how this will influence the direction of the curriculum.

The participants will have to sum up their work on a poster which they will present in a final poster session at the workshop. The results from the workshop will be compared to results from interviews with experts from Nordic universities on how they expect the future to look like.

Discussions on the challenges engineering education will have to address and how engineering 2030 could be imagined is of vital importance for both researchers and practitioners working with development of European engineering education.

The results will be summarized and spread to the SEFI forum, and may also be the base for further investigations on future Engineering Education.